

ABIS EDUCATION INITIATIVE REPORT

Sustainable, Responsible & Ethical Business Education:

An Analysis of Full Programmes in the ABIS Network

The Academy of Business in Society

ABIS GLOBAL EDUCATION INITIATIVE

Sustainable, Responsible & Ethical Business Education: An Analysis of Full Programmes in the ABIS Network

Contents

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	2
I/ SYNOPSIS	4
II/ AGGREGATE FIGURES	5
APPENDIX I: TABLE OF MEMBER PROGRAMMES.....	9
APPENDIX II: LIST OF TAG WORDS	21

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

ABIS - The Academy of Business in Society has launched a new (Global) Education Initiative to support the realization of its mission, to strengthen the exchange of institutional innovation, to drive innovation in business schools and universities, and ultimately to co-create a future blueprint for business and management education adapted to the complexities and challenges of the 21st century.

As a first step, between February and July 2016, ABIS - The Academy of Business in Society has focused on gathering and analysing data about full programmes dedicated to Sustainable, Responsible & Ethical (SRE) Business Education offered by its members. The overall objective of this phase was to map and estimate members' SRE educational. This report provides an overview of this mapping exercise.

A total of 152 SRE programmes have been identified. These are offered by 52 institutions, which currently represent 76% of ABIS Academic Partners & Members, across nearly 20 countries.

A vast majority of programmes are offered at Graduate level (43%), followed by Executive Education (29%). Doctoral and MBA programmes reach a similar share, each representing 10% of the programmes. At undergraduate level, only 9 programmes have been identified (6%).

Reflecting the structure of the network, programmes offered by European institutions dominate the educational offer (67%). Around 30% of the programmes are jointly offered by members in Asia and Middle East and Africa.

In each of these geographic areas, there is a slightly different focus on various SRE themes. In Europe, "General Sustainability" is at the core of almost 40% of the programmes, but attention is also devoted to a wide range of other SRE issues. "Development Studies" (25%), "Social Impact" (25%) and "Social Entrepreneurship" (15%) dominate the educational offer in Middle East and Africa, whereas half of the programmes offered by Asian institutions have a strong focus on "Environmental Management".

Overall, the offered programmes were most often associated with "General Sustainability", "Environmental Management" and "Sustainable Development".

The results of this first analysis will serve as a basis to capture and learn from the experience of those members which have 'broken through the glass ceiling' (of electives, stand-alone modules and events, and peripheral attention paid to the field), and embarked on strategic integration of SRE themes across its portfolio of educational programmes.

In 2017, the Education Initiative will pursue two main goals:

- To collate network insights and perspectives on the drivers and key success factors behind mainstreaming corporate responsibility, ethics and sustainability at the institutional level, for the wider benefit of the full ABIS community;
- To establish a dynamic group of members willing to experiment and pilot new approaches to education and learning taking into consideration the forthcoming blueprint for skills, competences and mindsets of the ABIS corporate-led Global Talent Forum.

Overall, the ambition is to position the ABIS network as something far more than an academic “talking shop” about potential changes in management education around responsibility, ethics and sustainability issues, with the aim to build stronger bridges between our corporate and academic audiences and with a long-term view of co-creating new models of business education and talent development that equip current and future graduates of *all* management training programmes to shape a more sustainable future.

I/ SYNOPSIS

As the first step in ABIS' new Global Education Initiative, the central team has conducted an initial mapping of full programmes, offered by our academic members, that are likely to expose students on how to integrate social and environmental impact into their (current or future) managerial roles.

Data have been primarily collected through online desk research from member websites and related brochures / marketing material. Where possible, we have done an initial analysis across both geographic regions and the spectrum of full-time management / business education programmes: undergraduate, graduate, executive, doctoral, and other.

The selection of the programmes was determined by the occurrences of specific tag words in the programme title and/or short description. Our subsequent analysis was based on linking such tag words to the main themes of SRE business in society.

The complete list of the identified programmes can be found in Appendix I and the list of related tag words in Appendix II.

NOTE

We recognize the limitations of online desk research and application of SRE-specific tag words. Although we have asked our members to review the first version of the report and to improve our coverage, we acknowledge that there may be some gaps with respect to the actual portfolio of programmes.

As such, this report is not to be considered as the result of an intensive and methodical research, but rather as an extensive mapping exercise to raise the awareness around the general state of the art of Sustainable, Responsible & Ethical Business Education and to inspire collaboration and cross-pollination of ideas to advance change in business education.

II/ AGGREGATE FIGURES

Insights from the available data are shown in the following tables and figures.

The programmes' distribution according to the different educational levels is displayed below:

Educational Level	N° of programmes
Undergraduate	9
Graduate	65
MBA	15
PhD	15
Ex. Education	45
Others	3
Total	152

Table 1. Programme distribution per education level

Figure 2. Programme distribution per education level

A geographic distribution analysis was also conducted. The geographic areas were identified as: Asia, Europe, Middle East and Africa, North and South America and Oceania.

Naturally, the distribution of programmes mirrors the academic members' distribution in the various geographic areas. Given the limited number of members in the American continent, no programmes were identified in that area. The table and figure below thus refer to the other four areas.

Geographic distribution	N° of programs	N° of members
Asia	25	5
Europe	102	58
Middle East and Africa	24	4
Oceania	1	1
Total	152	68

Table 2. Programme distribution per geographic area

Figure 2. Programme distribution per geographic area

Categories (24)	N° of mentions
General Sustainability	48
Environmental Management	25
Sustainable Development	13
CSR	12
Development Studies	11
Leadership	11
Ethics	10
Energy	9
Social Impact	9
Sustainable Business	8
Social Entrepreneurship	8
Sustainability Policy	7
Management	6
Futures Studies	5
Social Innovation	5
Responsible Management	5
NGO	5
Climate Change	4
Innovation	4
Entrepreneurship	4
Sustainability Management	3
Sustainable Innovation	2
Sustainable Management	2
Other	29

Table 3. Programme categories

A total of 93 tag words related to programmes were identified (see Appendix II). In order to enable more meaningful analysis, the tag words were grouped in 24 categories (Table 3) that reflect more general, relevant topics in the field of responsible management, ethics and sustainability.

The following bar charts and histograms show which are the most popular categories (based on frequency) covered by the identified programmes in general (Figure 3) and per geographic area (Figures 4-7).

Lastly, Figure 8 provides a more condensed view on how the most popular categories are distributed and which ones dominate the educational offer across geographic areas.

Figure 3. Most popular programme categories

Figure 4. Most popular programme categories in Asia

Figure 5. Most popular programme categories in Europe

Figure 6. Most popular programme categories in Middle East and Africa

Figure 7. Most popular programme categories in Oceania*

*The figure related to Oceania is based on only one programme, it is therefore not to be considered as representative. For the same reason, Oceania was excluded from the chart below.

Figure 8. Programme categories per geographic area

APPENDIX I: TABLE OF MEMBER PROGRAMMES

Programme	Institution	Education level ¹	Country	Geographic area	Category
Executive Master in Social Entrepreneurship (MHUSE)	ALTIS - Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore	E	Italy	Europe	General Sustainability NGO Social Entrepreneurship Social Impact
Master in Global Business and Sustainability	ALTIS - Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore	G	Italy	Europe	Sustain General Sustainability
Global MBA in Impact Entrepreneurship	ALTIS - Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore, in collaboration with African Universities	MBA	Italy	Europe	General Sustainability Social Entrepreneurship
MSc in Sustainability and Responsibility	Ashridge Business School	G	UK	Europe	CSR General Sustainability
Master in Development Management	Asian Institute of Management	G	Philippines	Asia	Development Studies
Program for Development Managers	Asian Institute of Management	E	Philippines	Asia	Development Studies
Leadership and Management of Change for Development Managers	Asian Institute of Management	E	Philippines	Asia	Development Studies Other
Designing and Developing Sustainable Tourism	Asian Institute of Management	E	Philippines	Asia	Other
Master in Climate Change and Sustainable Development	Asian Institute of Technology	G	Thailand	Asia	Climate Change Sustainable Development
Master in Environmental Engineering and Management	Asian Institute of Technology	G	Thailand	Asia	Environmental Management
Master in Gender and Development Studies	Asian Institute of Technology	G	Thailand	Asia	Development Studies Other

¹ U= Undergraduate, G=Graduate, D=PhD, E=Executive, O= Other i.e. DBA and Summer schools

Programme	Institution	Education level ^a	Country	Geographic area	Category
Master in Urban Environmental Management	Asian Institute of Technology	G	Thailand	Asia	Environmental Management
Master of Natural Resources Management	Asian Institute of Technology	G	Thailand	Asia	Environmental Management
MBA in Energy Business Management	Asian Institute of Technology	MBA	Thailand	Asia	Energy
PhD in Climate Change and Sustainable Development	Asian Institute of Technology	D	Thailand	Asia	Climate Change Sustainable Development
PhD in Environmental Engineering and Management	Asian Institute of Technology	D	Thailand	Asia	Environmental Management
PhD in Gender and Development Studies	Asian Institute of Technology	D	Thailand	Asia	Development Studies Other
PhD of Natural Resources Management	Asian Institute of Technology	D	Thailand	Asia	Environmental Management
PhD in Urban Environmental Management	Asian Institute of Technology	D	Thailand	Asia	Environmental Management
Certificat Construire Son Rapport Rse Developpement Durable	Audencia Business School	E	France	Europe	CSR
EuroMBA	Audencia Business School	MBA	France	Europe	Management CSR Other
MBA in Responsible Management	Audencia Business School	MBA	France	Europe	Responsible Management
Executive Master of Management in Energy	BI Norwegian Business School	E	Norway	Europe	Energy
Executive MBA Energy	BI Norwegian Business School	MBA	Norway	Europe	Energy
MSc in BA - Entrepreneurship & Social Innovation	Catholic University of Eichstätt-Ingolstadt	G	Germany	Europe	Entrepreneurship Social Innovation General Sustainability
Consultoría Social Empresarial	Comillas Pontifical University	O	Spain	Europe	Social Entrepreneurship
Inside Kenya. Development, Emerging economies, and International relations	Comillas Pontifical University	O	Spain	Europe	Development Studies Other

Programme	Institution	Education level ^a	Country	Geographic area	Category
Inside Washington Tech. Technology, Politics and Sustainable development	Comillas Pontifical University	O	Spain	Europe	Entrepreneurship Social Entrepreneurship Sustainable Development
PhD in Business and Regional Competitiveness, Innovation and Sustainability	Comillas Pontifical University	D	Spain	Europe	General Sustainability Innovation Other
MSc in Business Administration and Bioentrepreneurship	Copenhagen Business School	G	Denmark	Europe	Entrepreneurship
MSc in Business Administration and Philosophy	Copenhagen Business School	G	Denmark	Europe	CSR Ethics General Sustainability Other
The Copenhagen Full-time MBA	Copenhagen Business School	MBA	Denmark	Europe	Responsible Management
BSc in Environmental Management	Coventry University	U	UK	Europe	Environmental Management
BSc in Oil, Gas and Energy Management	Coventry University	U	UK	Europe	Energy
MSc in Agroecology and Food Security	Coventry University	G	UK	Europe	Climate Change Environmental Management Other
MSc in Environmental Management	Coventry University	G	UK	Europe	Environmental Management
Embedding Corporate Responsibility & Sustainability	Cranfield School of Management	E	UK	Europe	CSR General Sustainability
MSc in Management and Corporate Sustainability	Cranfield School of Management	G	UK	Europe	General Sustainability
Environmental Management for Business	Cranfield School of Management* *Cranfield University	G	UK	Europe	Environmental Management

Programme	Institution	Education level ²	Country	Geographic area	Category
Environmental Risk Management	Cranfield School of Management* *Cranfield University	G	UK	Europe	Environmental Management
MSc in Environmental and Natural Resource Economics	Durham University Business School	G	UK	Europe	General Sustainability
MSc in Management (Business Ethics)	Durham University Business School	G	UK	Europe	Ethics Management
MSc in Global Business & Sustainability	Erasmus University, Rotterdam School of Management	G	Netherlands	Europe	General Sustainability Other
PhD in Management Sciences - Social Innovation	ESADE Business School	D	Spain	Europe	Social Innovation
Postgraduate Diploma in Management - Leadership and Social Responsibility	ESMT European School of Management and Technology	E	Germany	Europe	Leadership Social Impact
Executive MBA	ESMT European School of Management and Technology	MBA	Germany	Europe	Leadership Other
MBA	ESMT European School of Management and Technology	MBA	Germany	Europe	Leadership Other
BA in Business & Sustainability Management	European University Business School	U	Switzerland	Europe	Management Sustainability Management
MSc in Environmental Change, Management and Monitoring	Hull University Business School	G	UK	Europe	Environmental Management
MSc in Renewable Energy	Hull University Business School	G	UK	Europe	Energy
PhD in Business Ethics	IESE	D	Spain	Europe	Ethics
MBA - Sustainability	Inha University, College of Business Administration	MBA	South Korea	Asia	General Sustainability Leadership
Leading the Business of Sustainability	INSEAD	E	France	Europe	General Sustainability Leadership
Green Management Programme	ISTUD Foundation	G	Italy	Europe	Sustainable Management
The Kent MBA	Kent Business School	MBA	UK	Europe	Responsible Management

Programme	Institution	Education level ^a	Country	Geographic area	Category
LLM in Environmental Law and Sustainability	Kingston University Business School* *Faculty of Law	G	UK	Europe	General Sustainability Sustainability Policy
MSc in Sustainability & Environmental Change	Kingston University Business School* *Faculty of Science, Engineering and Computing	G	UK	Europe	General Sustainability
MSc in Sustainable Environmental Development with Management Studies	Kingston University Business School* *Faculty of Science, Engineering and Computing	G	UK	Europe	Sustainable Development
Erasmus Mundus Joint Master Degree in Pervasive Computing and Communications for Sustainable Development (PERCCOM)	Lappeenranta University of Technology	G	Finland	Europe	Other Sustainable Development Innovation
Master in Strategy, Innovation and Sustainability	Lappeenranta University of Technology	G	Finland	Europe	General Sustainability Other
Master's Programme in Sustainability Science and Solutions	Lappeenranta University of Technology	G	Finland	Europe	General Sustainability
PhD in Environmental Technology	Lappeenranta University of Technology	D	Finland	Europe	Sustainable Innovation
PhD in Green Chemical Technology	Lappeenranta University of Technology	D	Finland	Europe	Sustainable Innovation
BSc of Environmental Sciences	Leuphana University, Centre for Sustainability Management	U	Germany	Europe	General Sustainability
MBA in Sustainability Management	Leuphana University, Centre for Sustainability Management	MBA	Germany	Europe	General Sustainability
MSc in Global Sustainability Science	Leuphana University, Centre for Sustainability Management	G	Germany	Europe	General Sustainability
MSc in Sustainability Science	Leuphana University, Centre for Sustainability Management	G	Germany	Europe	General Sustainability
Corporate Social Responsibility	Maastricht University	E	Netherlands	Europe	CSR Ethics
MSc in Sustainability Science and Policy	Maastricht University	G	Netherlands	Europe	General Sustainability

Programme	Institution	Education level ^a	Country	Geographic area	Category
					Sustainability Policy
PhD in Sustainability Science and Policy	Maastricht University	D	Netherlands	Europe	General Sustainability Sustainability Policy
BSc in Management - Innovation, Sustainability and Entrepreneurship	Manchester Business School	U	UK	Europe	General Sustainability
BSc in Management - Sustainable and Ethical Business	Manchester Business School	U	UK	Europe	Ethics General Sustainability
Master in Energy Management	MIP - Politecnico di Milano	E	Italy	Europe	Energy
NBS MBA	Nottingham Trent University, Nottingham Business School	MBA	UK	Europe	Management Responsible Management
Behavioral and Cultural Governance	Nyenrode Business University	E	Netherlands	Europe	Ethics
CSR Expedition	Nyenrode Business University	E	Netherlands	Europe	CSR General Sustainability
Green Business Modelling	Nyenrode Business University	E	Netherlands	Europe	Other
Inclusive Business Academy	Nyenrode Business University	E	Netherlands	Europe	Innovation Social Impact Sustainable Business
Integrity Implementation	Nyenrode Business University	E	Netherlands	Europe	Ethics
Masterclass Professional Future Strategist	Nyenrode Business University	E	Netherlands	Europe	Futures Studies
MBA Public & Private	Nyenrode Business University	MBA	Netherlands	Europe	General Sustainability Other
Mini MBA Energy Transition And Innovation	Nyenrode Business University	E	Netherlands	Europe	Energy General Sustainability
Social Entrepreneurship	Nyenrode Business University	E	Netherlands	Europe	Social Entrepreneurship
Sustainability, Leadership and Decision Making: Learning from Failures and Successes	Nyenrode Business University	E	Netherlands	Europe	Sustainable Development General Sustainability

Programme	Institution	Education level ^a	Country	Geographic area	Category
					Leadership
Teal Summer Journey	Nyenrode Business University	E	Netherlands	Europe	Sustainable Development Innovation Leadership Other
BSc Management with Sustainability	Royal Holloway University of London, School of Management	U	UK	Europe	General Sustainability Management
MSc in Sustainability and Management	Royal Holloway University of London, School of Management	G	UK	Europe	General Sustainability Social Innovation
Master in Green Management, Energy and Corporate Social Responsibility	SDA Bocconi School of Management* Universita' Bocconi	G	Italy	Europe	CSR Energy Sustainable Management
Advanced Master in Innovation & Entrepreneurship	Solvay Brussels School	G	Belgium	Europe	Entrepreneurship Innovation
European Microfinance Programme	Solvay Brussels School	G	Belgium	Europe	Other
Executive Program in Management and Philosophy	Solvay Brussels School	E	Belgium	Europe	Management Other
Africa Business & Sustainability Programme	Strathmore Business School	E	Kenya	Middle East and Africa	General Sustainability Other
B.A. Development Studies & Philosophy	Strathmore Business School	U	Kenya	Middle East and Africa	Development Studies Other
Impact Business Leaders Programme	Strathmore Business School	E	Kenya	Middle East and Africa	Social Impact Leadership
Leadership for Sustainable Development	Strathmore Business School	E	Kenya	Middle East and Africa	Sustainable Development
Master of Applied Philosophy & Ethics	Strathmore Business School	G	Kenya	Middle East and Africa	Ethics

Programme	Institution	Education level ^a	Country	Geographic area	Category
					Other
Sustainable Advanced Management Programme	Strathmore Business School	E	Kenya	Middle East and Africa	Sustainability Management
MSc in Environmental Management and Engineering	The Hong Kong Polytechnic University	G	Hong Kong	Asia	Environmental Management
MSc in Sustainable Urban Development	The Hong Kong Polytechnic University	G	Hong Kong	Asia	Sustainable Development
MSc in Environmental Health and Safety	The Hong Kong University of Science and Technology (HKUST)	G	Hong Kong	Asia	Environmental Management
Mphil in Environmental Engineering	The Hong Kong University of Science and Technology (HKUST)	G	Hong Kong	Asia	Environmental Management
MPhil in Environmental Science, Policy and Management	The Hong Kong University of Science and Technology (HKUST)	G	Hong Kong	Asia	General Sustainability Environmental Management Sustainability Policy
MSc in Environmental Engineering and Management	The Hong Kong University of Science and Technology (HKUST)	G	Hong Kong	Asia	Environmental Management
MSc in Environmental Science and Management	The Hong Kong University of Science and Technology (HKUST)	G	Hong Kong	Asia	General Sustainability Environmental Management
PhD in Environmental Engineering	The Hong Kong University of Science and Technology (HKUST)	D	Hong Kong	Asia	Environmental Management
International Programme on the Management of Sustainability	TIAS School for Business and Society	E	Netherlands	Europe	Sustainability Management
Master of Public and Non-Profit Management	TIAS School for Business and Society	E	Netherlands	Europe	NGO
Sustainability Management	TUM School of Management	E	Germany	Europe	General Sustainability
MA in Futures Studies	Turku School of Economics	G	Finland	Europe	Futures Studies
Joint Research Master's in Business in Society	University of Amsterdam, Amsterdam Business School	G	Netherlands	Europe	CSR Ethics General Sustainability
Leadership Programme for Sustainable Development in the Health and Care Sector	University of Cambridge Institute for Sustainability Leadership	E	UK	Europe	General Sustainability Other
Master of Studies in Sustainability Leadership	University of Cambridge	G	UK	Europe	General Sustainability

Programme	Institution	Education level ^a	Country	Geographic area	Category
	Institute for Sustainability Leadership				Leadership
Postgraduate Certificate in Sustainable Business	University of Cambridge Institute for Sustainability Leadership	G	UK	Europe	Sustainable Business
Postgraduate Certificate in Sustainable Value Chains	University of Cambridge Institute for Sustainability Leadership	G	UK	Europe	Sustainable Business
Postgraduate Diploma in Sustainable Business	University of Cambridge Institute for Sustainability Leadership	G	UK	Europe	Sustainable Business
Sustainability Leadership Laboratories	University of Cambridge Institute for Sustainability Leadership	G	UK	Europe	General Sustainability
Sustainability Practitioner Programme	University of Cambridge Institute for Sustainability Leadership	E	UK	Europe	General Sustainability
The Prince of Wales's Business & Sustainability Programme	University of Cambridge	E	UK	Europe	Leadership
	Institute for Sustainability Leadership	E	UK	Europe	General Sustainability
Executive MBA	University of Cape Town, Graduate School of Business	MBA	South Africa	Middle East and Africa	Other Social Impact Sustainable Business
Impact Investing in Africa	University of Cape Town, Graduate School of Business	E	South Africa	Middle East and Africa	Other Social Impact
Master of Philosophy specializing in Inclusive Innovation	University of Cape Town, Graduate School of Business	G	South Africa	Middle East and Africa	Social Innovation
Masters in Commerce in Development Finance	University of Cape Town, Graduate School of Business	G	South Africa	Middle East and Africa	Development Studies NGO
Social Entrepreneurship	University of Cape Town, Graduate School of Business	E	South Africa	Middle East and Africa	Social Entrepreneurship
Strategic Social Engagement Practice	University of Cape Town, Graduate School of Business	E	South Africa	Middle East and Africa	Social Impact
MSc Global Challenges	University of Edinburgh Business School	G	UK	Europe	General Sustainability Other Sustainable Development
MSc in Carbon Finance	University of Edinburgh Business School	G	UK	Europe	Climate Change

Programme	Institution	Education level ^a	Country	Geographic area	Category
					Energy Other
One Planet MBA	University of Exeter Business School	MBA	UK	Europe	Environmental Management Other Social Impact Sustainable Business
MSc in Environmental Sciences	University of Koblenz-Landau, Central Institute for Scientific Entrepreneurship & International Transfer* *Faculty of Natural and Environmental Sciences	G	Germany	Europe	General Sustainability
BSc in Environmental Science	University of Limerick	U	Ireland	Europe	General Sustainability
MSc in Sustainable Resource Management: Policy & Practice	University of Limerick	G	Ireland	Europe	Environmental Management Sustainability Management Sustainability Policy
PhD in Marketing and Reputation	University of Reading, Henley Business School	D	UK	Europe	CSR General Sustainability Marketing
Disability and Inclusiveness: The Business Case	University of Stellenbosch Business School	E	South Africa	Middle East and Africa	Social Impact
Ethics Officer Certification Programme	University of Stellenbosch Business School	E	South Africa	Middle East and Africa	Ethics
Management Programme for NPOs	University of Stellenbosch Business School	E	South Africa	Middle East and Africa	NGO
MPhil in Development Finance	University of Stellenbosch Business School	G	South Africa	Middle East and Africa	Development Studies
MPhil in Futures Studies	University of Stellenbosch Business School	G	South Africa	Middle East and Africa	Futures Studies

Programme	Institution	Education level ^a	Country	Geographic area	Category
NPO Leadership and Strategy Programme	University of Stellenbosch Business School	E	South Africa	Middle East and Africa	NGO
PhD in Development Finance	University of Stellenbosch Business School	D	South Africa	Middle East and Africa	Development Studies
PhD in Futures Studies	University of Stellenbosch Business School	D	South Africa	Middle East and Africa	Futures Studies
Postgraduate Diploma in Development Finance	University of Stellenbosch Business School	G	South Africa	Middle East and Africa	Development Studies
Postgraduate Diploma in Futures Studies	University of Stellenbosch Business School	G	South Africa	Middle East and Africa	Futures Studies
Postgraduate Diploma in Leadership Development	University of Stellenbosch Business School	G	South Africa	Middle East and Africa	Leadership
Social Innovation and Entrepreneurship	University of Stellenbosch Business School	E	South Africa	Middle East and Africa	Social Entrepreneurship Social Innovation
Creating Sustainable Behaviour Change	University of the West of England	E	UK	Europe	General Sustainability
LLM in Environmental Law and Sustainable Development	University of the West of England	G	UK	Europe	Sustainability Policy Sustainable Development
MSc in Environmental Management	University of the West of England	G	UK	Europe	Environmental Management
MSc in Sustainable Development in Practice	University of the West of England	G	UK	Europe	General Sustainability Sustainable Development
Sustainable Development: Principles and Practice	University of the West of England	E	UK	Europe	Sustainable Development
Sustainable Transport Management and Operations	University of the West of England	E	UK	Europe	Sustainable Business
The Sustainable Organisation: Vision into practice	University of the West of England	E	UK	Europe	Environmental Management General Sustainability Sustainable Business
	Waikato Management School	G		Oceania	CSR

Programme	Institution	Education level ^a	Country	Geographic area	Category
Master of Management Studies in Management and Sustainability			New Zealand		Environmental Management General Sustainability

APPENDIX II: LIST OF TAG WORDS

Tag words (93)		
Africa	Food Security	Responsible Management
Business Ethics	Forward Thinking	Risk Management
Business Model Innovation	Futures Studies	Scenario Planning
Business Philosophy	Gender Studies	Shareholder Value
Change Processes	Global Business	Social Enterprise
Climate Change	Green Business Funding	Social Entrepreneurship
Competitiveness	Green Management	Social Impact
Corporate Responsibility	Green Technology	Social Innovation
CSR	Health Care Sector	Social Performance
Design Thinking	Health Challenges	Social Responsibility
Development Finance	ICT	Social Sustainability
Development Studies	Impact entrepreneurship	Societal Value
Energy	Impact Investing	Strategy
Energy Business Management	Inclusiveness	Sustainability
Energy Finance	Innovation	Sustainability Management
Energy Management	Integrity	Sustainability Policy
Energy Technology	Intrapreneurship	Sustainability Science
Entrepreneurship	Leadership	Sustainable Business
Environmental change	Management	Sustainable Business Model
Environmental Development	Marketing	Sustainable Change
Environmental Economics	Microfinance	Sustainable Development
Environmental Engineering	Natural Resources	Sustainable Energy Management
Environmental Impact	Natural Resources Management	Sustainable Innovation
Environmental Law	NGOs	Sustainable Management
Environmental Management	Non-Profit Management	Sustainable Operations
Environmental Problems	Partnerships	Sustainable Organization
Environmental Sciences	Philosophy	Sustainable Tourism
Environmental Sustainability	Renewable Energy	Sustainable Urban Development
Environmental Technology	Reputation	Sustainable Value Chains
Ethical leadership	Responsibility	Systemic Management
Ethics	Responsible Investment	Urban Environmental Management

Table I. List of tag words

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